

Isolation and detection of vanA and mecA resistance genes in Staphylococcus aureus from patients with osteomyelitis in Qom by multiplex PCR method

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Abstract

New research indicates an increase in the identification of methicillin-resistant staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) and vancomycin in patients with osteomyelitis. This study was conducted to identify the amount of MRSA and vancomycin carriers and determine antibiotic resistance in these patients. This research is cross-sectional and descriptive. 50 clinical samples were collected from patients in Qom (Iran) hospitals. Staphylococcus aureus was definitively diagnosed using catalase, coagulase, gram staining, mannitol fermentation, and DNase tests. Antibiotic discs were used to check the resistance level of the isolates. The presence of mecA and vanA genes in the isolates was confirmed using PCR. 19 Staphylococcus aureus were isolated from the samples. Examination of antibiotic sensitivity showed that 100% of pathogens are resistant to cefoxitin and vancomycin, 5 isolates have vanA gene, and the mecA gene was observed in all isolates. The issue of treating osteomyelitis and choosing the best antibiotic against the responsible microorganism remains a controversial challenge among physicians. The importance of antimicrobial therapy is obvious, while the optimal antibiotic regimen is still not well defined. Delay inadequate or inappropriate antimicrobial treatment may lead to severe disabilities including chronic pain, need for amputation, repeated surgeries, and ultimately increase the disease burden.

Keywords: Staphylococcus aureus, antibiotic resistance, osteomyelitis.

1. Introduction

Osteomyelitis is a fiery bone infection auxiliary to disease, which may be intense or inveterate. Side effects of intense osteomyelitis incorporate torment, fever, and edema of the influenced zone, and patients as a rule display bone rot within days to weeks of the starting disease. Constant osteomyelitis occurs after months to a long time of tireless contamination and may be characterized by necrotic bone and skin-to-bone fistulae [1, 2].

Osteomyelitis is classified as hematogenous or non-hematogenous based on the instrument of contamination. With hematogenous osteomyelitis, microscopic organisms travel to the bone auxiliary to circulatory system contamination, and the malady is more common in children, more seasoned grown-ups, and immunocompromised populations [1-3]. Non-hematogenous osteomyelitis happens from coordinated immunization at the location of surgery or injury or by spreading from adjoining delicate tissue and joint contaminations [1, 2].

Staphylococcus aureus is a bacterial pathogen that can cause a variety of diseases, including purulent or non-purulent (toxin-

mediated) infections, including skin and skin structure infections, as well as bone infections in children. *Staphylococcus aureus* in cases of endocarditis. Infectious, eye infections, septicemia, pneumonia, and central nervous system infections have also been identified. In order to design the appropriate empirical treatment and timely deal with this dangerous pathogen, professionals should be aware of the resistance patterns of *Staphylococcus aureus* in their communities, including resistance to methicillin and clindamycin [4].

Staphylococcus aureus is a gram-positive pathogen of humans and animals [5, 6], which can cause various diseases from simple skin infections to blood infections such as bacteremia or septicemia [7]. The biofilm secreted by *Staphylococcus aureus* causes resistance to antibacterial drugs and minimizes its effect [8]. Antibiotic resistance is a serious threat to human and animal life, which is increasing annually due to the reduction of the effectiveness of many traditional antimicrobial drugs [9]. *Staphylococcus aureus* prevents antimicrobial drugs by forming a biofilm [10].

The formation of biofilm is related to various factors such as temperature changes, water depletion, and lack of nutrients [11, 12].

Staphylococci are the most common pathogenic pathogens isolated from patients and account for approximately 50% of bloodstream infections and 30% of hospital infections [13, 14], therefore increasing drug resistance in this pathogen is a serious threat to public health [15].

Staphylococci resistance to antimicrobial agents has been a global concern for several decades. This resistance is caused by the presence of various genes, including the *vanA* gene, which is one of the several identified vancomycin resistance genes. This gene is highly resistant to vancomycin and teicoplanin antibiotics [16].

One of the most important causes of nosocomial infections worldwide is methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). This high-level resistance to methicillin is caused by the *mecA* gene, which encodes an alternative penicillin-binding protein, PBP 2a [17].

The current research aims to isolate and trace resistance genes *vanA* and *mecA* in *Staphylococcus aureus* from patients with osteomyelitis in Qom City by multiplex PCR method.

2. Material and Methods

This research is cross-sectional and descriptive. 50 clinical samples were collected from patients in Qom (Iran) hospitals. The samples were cultured in a selective culture medium containing salt agar or sugar mannitol agar. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours under aerobic conditions. Isolation of *Staphylococcus aureus* is cultured on Blood agar medium Nutrient agar [18].

2.1 Isolation and biochemical identification of *Staphylococcus aureus*

The samples were cultured on blood agar medium by sterile plate method and at 37°C for 48 hours. Colonies were initially diagnosed by gram staining and catalase test. Then they were cultured on mannitol salt agar and DNase medium by dividing the plates into several parts in the form of small lines for 24 hours. The coagulase test was used as a confirmatory test for *Staphylococcus aureus* [19].

2.2 Determining antibiotic sensitivity

The antibiotic sensitivity is determined by the Kirby & Bauer standard method. Mueller's Hinton Agar medium was used as a selective medium, as well as penicillin (P), chloramphenicol (C), gentamicin (GN), trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (SXT), oxacillin (OX), erythromycin (E), ceftiofloxacin (FOX), tetracycline

(T), clindamycin (CC), vancomycin (V), rifampicin (RA) and ciprofloxacin (CIP) from Mast UK in this study. the microbial suspension was equal to the turbidity of the standard tube (McFarland's 05 solution) was used.

2.3 Phenotypic identification of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates resistant to methicillin and vancomycin

2.3.1 Oxacillin disc

This method was performed using a 1 microgram Oxacillin disc from MAST company (according to the company's standard method, 5-9-3). The presence of non-growth halo up to 10 mm was considered as methicillin resistant strain. Also, we considered semi-sensitive strains with 11-12 mm non-growth halo as methicillin resistant strains [20].

2.3.2 Cefoxitin disc

This method was performed using the 30 microgram Cefoxitin disk of MAST company (according to the company's standard method, 5-9-3). We considered the presence of non-growth halo up to 21 mm as methicillin resistant strain [21].

2.3.4 Oxacillin Screen Agar

The resistant samples were transferred to the Mueller Hinton agar medium containing 4% NaCl and 6 µg/ml oxacillin, the medium was incubated for 24 hours and the growth results were observed.

2.3.5 Vancomycin Test

The minimum concentration of vancomycin growth inhibitor is determined by the Broth Macro Dilution. A 24-hour suspension of bacteria was prepared in 5 ml of normal saline to half McFarland turbidity. Then 1/10 ml of suspension was diluted in 9.9 ml of normal saline and the volume was brought to 10 ml. Muller Hinton Broth culture medium was used to perform MIC. After 24 hours of incubation at 37 C, the minimum inhibitory concentration was read according to Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) instructions.

2.3.6 Determination of MIC to oxacillin in resistant strains

A stock of 512 µg/ml was prepared from oxacillin. Tubes containing 1 ml of Mueller Hinton Broth culture medium were prepared and 1 ml of stock was transferred to tube 1 and dilution preparation was done up to tube 10. Tubes 11 and 12 were considered negative and positive controls.

After that, 100 microliters of McFarland's 0/5 suspension were added to each tube from the resistant strain, and the tubes were kept in the incubator for 24 hours. The tube was considered MIC before growth.

Table 1: Antibiotic used and its MIC range according to CLSI guidelines

Antibiotic type	MIC resistant µg/ml	MIC sensitive µg/ml
oxacillin	4≥	≤ 2

2.4 Investigating the presence of resistance genes

Specific primers given in Table 2 were used to check the presence of genes in the investigated pathogens. Also, the reaction temperature is given in Table 3.

Table 2: mecA and vanA gene primers

Primer name	Primer sequence	TM	Size band
vanA-F	5'- TGGCAGCTACGTTTACCTATCCT - 3'	54°C	320 bp
vanA-R	5'- TGCTGAAAGGTCTGCGGG -3'	54°C	
Mec F	5'-TGATTCAGGTTACGGACAAGGTG- 3'	54°C	403 bp
Mec R	5'-ACCTGAGATTTTGGCATTGTAGC- 3'	54°C	

Table 3.: Temperature program for the multiplication of target genes

Temperature	Time	Cycle(s)
95	3 min	1
95	30 sec	35
54	35 sec	
72	35sec	
72	5 min	1

3. Results

3.1 Isolation and diagnosis of Staphylococcus aureus

From the collected samples, 19 isolates of Staphylococcus aureus were collected. The criterion for confirming Staphylococcus aureus isolates was the morphological and biochemical characteristics of this bacterium. This means that the samples taken in the transfer medium containing 7% salt were transferred to the blood agar medium after 24 to 48 hours and were cultured

on the mannitol salt agar and DNase medium based on the characteristics of the colony morphology and gram staining. If any of the tests were positive, a coagulase slide was performed (Fig 1). Tubular coagulase was performed if slide coagulase was negative. After diagnosis, the samples whose biochemical characteristics were consistent with the characteristics of Staphylococcus aureus were included as positive samples and the corresponding colonies were saved.

Figure 1- Mannitol fermentation test
Yellow: positive test, red: negative test

3.2 Antibiotic resistance pattern of Staphylococcus aureus to antimicrobial drugs

The antibiotic sensitivity of 19 isolates of Staphylococcus aureus was determined by the agar disk diffusion method to the desired

antibiotics, based on the results of the highest sensitivity in the antibiotic cefoxitin with 100% and in vancomycin in 5 samples (strains no. 2, 4, 5, 12 and 19 are resistant to vancomycin) has been observed Table 2: Pneumonia Risk Factors in Children.

Table 4: Antibiotic sensitivity of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates by agar disk diffusion Test

CIP	RA	V	CC	T	FOX	E	OX	SXT	GN	C	P	
≥21	≥20	-	≥21	≥19	≥22	≥23	≥22	≥16	≥15	≥18	≥29	Sensitive
16-20	17-19	-	15-20	15-18	-	12-22	-	11-15	13-14	13-17	-	Intermediated
≤15	≤16	-	≤14	≤14	≤21	≤13	≤21	≤10	≤12	≤12	≤28	Resistance

Figure 2: Antibiotic sensitivity *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates

Figure 3: Determining antibiotic sensitivity by disk diffusion method

Determining the percentage of *Staphylococcus aureus* resistant to methicillin by genotyping

PCR test to identify the *mecA* gene on the isolated samples should create a 404 bp band on the gel based on the designed primers. The *mecA* gene was observed in 19 samples of this gene (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Examining the presence of genes *mecA*

Determining the percentage of vancomycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* genotypically

PCR test to identify the *vanA* gene on the isolated samples should create a 320 bp band on the gel based on the designed primers. The *vanA* gene was observed in 5 samples (Figures 5 and 6).

Figure 5: Examining the presence of genes *vanA*

Figure 6: Gel electrophoresis image resulting from Multiplex-PCR reaction

4. Discussion

In this study, 19 isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* were collected from the collected samples. The criterion for confirming *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates was the morphological and biochemical characteristics of this bacterium. After the diagnosis, the samples whose biochemical characteristics were consistent with the characteristics of *Staphylococcus aureus* were included as positive samples, and the corresponding colonies were saved. Based on the results, the highest sensitivity was observed in cefoxitin antibiotic with 100% and in vancomycin in 5 samples (strains no. 2, 4, 5, 12, and 19 are resistant to vancomycin).

PCR test to identify the *mecA* gene on the isolated samples that should create a 404 bp band on the gel electrophoresis based on the designed primers. which was observed in 19 samples of this gene. PCR test to identify the *vanA* gene on the isolated samples that should create a 320 bp band on the gel electrophoresis based on the designed primers. which was observed in 5 samples of this gene.

Kalantari et al. (2007) conducted a study in Tehran on 145 infectious samples with arthritis and osteomyelitis, 60% of the samples contained *Staphylococcus aureus*. 38% of isolates were

resistant to cloxacillin and 89% were sensitive to vancomycin and clindamycin [22].

In a 2020 study in America by Weiss et al. on 584 patients with osteomyelitis infection, 45% of the samples collected included methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus* [23]. A 2020 study in Tanzania by Silago et al., was conducted on 74 osteomyelitis samples, from which 63 *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria were isolated, 18% of which were resistant to methicillin [24].

5. Conclusion

All the investigated drugs can be a suitable treatment option in the treatment of infections caused by these bacteria in similar places. The results of our study showed that the prevalence of infections caused by this bacterium, which has no known underlying risk factors, is high. Due to the increase in the prevalence of this community-acquired bacteria that does not have a risk factor, it is necessary to take preventive measures to stop this process, which is a major health problem. According to the results of the present study, it is suggested to investigate and determine the presence of resistance genes in *Staphylococcus aureus* samples isolated from patients in other cities.

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